

plastic pot and 20 pots comprised each of 5 replications in a randomized block design. Another experiment used 10.5-cm-diam petri plates in the laboratory. In each plate, 100 seeds were placed on filter paper and 2 ml of distilled water was added. Each set was in three replications.

The pots were submerged, leaving seeds 10 cm below water level for 5 d in controlled tanks. Then the water level was reduced to 2 cm and maintained for 15 d, after which data were recorded.

Results of the pot experiment showed that 40% coating significantly increased the percentage germination for both cultivars (Table 1).

Results of the petri plate test indicated germination and seedling growth of both cultivars was reduced at both calcium peroxide concentrations (Table 2) perhaps because an alkaline medium developed from the solution of calcium peroxide in water. Further study is in progress. □

Table 1. Effect of calcium peroxide coating on germination of two rice cultivars under submerged conditions, Chinsurah, India.^a

Treatment	Germination ^b (%)	Mean shoot length (cm)	Mean root length (cm)
<i>NC492</i>			
CaO ₂ coated (40%)	86.6**	25.0	14.8
CaO ₂ coated (20%)	70.0**	23.3	14.1
Uncoated (dry)	16.6	24.2	12.8
Uncoated (sprouted)	35.0	23.9	13.0
<i>Jaladhi 2</i>			
CaO ₂ coated (40%)	73.3**	22.1	16.8
CaO ₂ coated (20%)	68.3 *	20.9	14.0
Uncoated (dry)	56.6	16.6	12.7
Uncoated (sprouted)	60.6	18.4	13.4

^aData were recorded 20 d after sowing. ^b*Significant at P = 0.05, **significant at P = 0.01.

Table 2. Effect of calcium peroxide coating on germination of two rice cultivars in petri plates in the laboratory, Chinsurah, India.^a

Treatment	Germination (%)	Mean shoot length (cm)	Mean root length (cm)
<i>NC492</i>			
CaO ₂ coated (40%)	62.0	7.2	3.5
CaO ₂ coated (20%)	69.0	11.2	6.5
Uncoated	100.0	14.6	11.5
<i>Juladhi 2</i>			
CaO ₂ coated (40%)	59.0	6.2	5.0
CaO ₂ coated (20%)	76.0	7.5	5.2
Uncoated	98.0	13.2	14.5

^aData were recorded after 10 d.

Effect of seedling age at transplanting and fertilizer levels on grain yield

B. H. Shahani, research officer, Agronomy, A. B. Khan, director, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Dera Ismail (D.I.) Khan; and M. A. Khan, lecturer in Agronomy, Faculty of Agriculture, Gomal University, D. I. Khan, N. W. F. P., Pakistan

We tested the performance of IR6 at different transplanting ages and 10 fertilizer levels at ARS and the Government Seed Farm Rakh Manghan in D. I. Khan in 1982. The experiment was in a split-plot design with three replications. Seedling ages were evaluated in main plots and fertility levels in subplots.

N, P, and K were broadcast and incorporated into dry soil before transplanting. A composite soil sample (0-25 cm) was analyzed (Table 1).

Grain yields for seedlings transplanted at different ages did not significantly differ (Table 2). Yield increased significantly as fertilizer levels were increased. The highest grain yield of 6.4 t/ha was obtained with 138-26-0 kg NPK/ha (Table 2). □

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of soils at two experimental sites in India.

Location	pH (1:5)	Ex ₁₀ ⁶ (1:5)	P (ppm)	K (ppm)	OM (%)	Texture
Agricultural Research Station	8.1	950	3	145	0.62	Clayey
Government Seed Farm Rakh Manghan	8.0	1200	2	124	0.72	Clayey

Table 2. Effect of seedling age and different fertilizer levels on rice (IR6) grain yield. D. I. Khan, NWFP, Pakistan, 1982.

Fertilizer applied (kg/ha)			Grain yield ^a (t/ha) of seedlings transplanted at			Av grain yield ^b (t/ha)
N	P	K	30 d	45 d	60 d	
0	0	0	3.4	3.6	2.9	3.3 f
46	0	0	4.5	4.8	4.5	4.6 e
92	0	0	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.4 bcd
138	0	0	6.3	6.3	5.9	6.7 ab
46	26	0	4.7	4.9	4.8	4.8 de
92	26	0	6.1	5.7	5.7	5.8 abc
138	26	0	6.9	6.4	6.0	6.4 a
46	26	50	4.5	5.3	4.9	4.9 cde
92	26	50	5.9	6.0	5.7	5.9 ab
138	26	50	5.8	6.2	6.2	6.1 ab
Average			5.3	5.5	5.2	

^aAv of 2 locations. ^bMeans followed by a similar letter are not significantly different at 5% level.